

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

Associations of Serum Testosterone and Sex Hormone–Binding Globulin with Incident Fractures in Men

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CONTENTS

Supplementary Methods	Page 2
Supplementary References	Page 4
Supplementary Table 1	Page 5
Supplementary Table 2	Page 6
Supplementary Table 3	Page 8
Supplementary Figure 1	Page 9
Supplementary Figure 2	Page 10
Supplementary Figure 3	Page 11
Supplementary Figure 4	Page 12

Supplementary Methods

Model predictors were derived from UK Biobank data using: self-report (infertility); hospital admission International Classification of Disease (ICD) diagnosis codes (adrenogenital/testicular disorders, malnutrition, vitamin D deficiency; Supplementary Table 1); medication usage data (androgens, antiandrogens, 5 α -reductase inhibitors or other hormone medications, anticonvulsant use, glucocorticoid use, opioid use, osteoporosis therapies, vitamin D supplementation, number of medications); a combination of self-report and ICD codes (COPD, malabsorption); self-report, ICD codes, and medication usage data (thyroid disease); self-report, ICD codes, and blood measurement (renal failure). Fracture in the past five years was identified using self-report (UK Biobank Variable 2463) and ICD codes in hospital admission data for any fracture, with a 5-year look-back. Secondary osteoporosis (comprised of men reporting type 1 diabetes, chronic liver disease or osteogenesis imperfecta), rheumatoid arthritis, and glucocorticoid use were identified using the variables and codes listed in Forgetta et al¹. Geographic region, alcohol consumption, living with partner, education, diet (red meat consumption), smoking status, and physical activity were categorised following methods reported in previous studies²⁻⁶. The number of medications taken at baseline was used as a proxy for overall comorbidity status and recoded into categories of 0, 1-2, 3-4, 5+ medications taken, consistent with previous NHS reporting^{7,8}.

Multivariate imputation by chained equations (MICE) was used to generate 40 multiply-imputed datasets for each analysis. Time-to-event data were log-transformed, and cubic polynomial terms constructed for variables that were modelled using restricted cubic splines, which approximates the “Just Another Variable” approach of von Hippel⁹. Missing values for the additional variables that were included to construct each cubic polynomial term were calculated using the specified polynomial function, instead of being imputed (i.e., were ‘passively’ imputed). Otherwise, predictive mean matching was used to impute continuous variables, logistic regression to impute binary

variables, and polytomous regression to impute factors with more than two levels. MICE imputations included the outcome (the censoring and log-transformed time-to-event variables) and all terms from the full model (Model 4 for total testosterone and SHBG analyses, and Model 3 for cFT analyses). BMI and waist circumference were not used together to impute other variables because they were highly correlated (Pearson's $r = 0.88$). Therefore, BMI was used in preference to waist circumference to impute the missing values of all variables, including of waist circumference. Due to the relatively large size of this dataset and computational demand, imputations were distributed across multiple cores using the 'futuremice' function of the 'mice' package, and depends on the 'furrr' package, with 20 iterations specified for each MICE imputation^{10,11}.

The multivariable Cox regressions were fitted using the 'cph' function of the 'rms' package¹². Per-variable and global tests of the proportional hazards were conducted from the fit of each model to the first of the imputed datasets and Schoenfeld residual plots inspected¹³. Terms demonstrating a departure from proportional hazards were analysed as stratification factors instead of as model terms¹⁴. Accordingly, the following predictors were analysed as stratification factors (in addition to geographic region, which was included as a stratification factor for all models – see Methods): fracture in past five years for analyses of any fracture and hip fracture in Models 2, 3, and 4 for T and SHBG exposures and in Models 2 and 3 for cFT; and physical activity for analyses of any fracture in Models 3 and 4 for T and SHBG. In each case, care was taken to ensure that incident events were recorded for all combinations of multiple cross-classified strata¹⁴. Pooled HR estimates and 95% CIs were obtained by firstly estimating log HRs using the 'Predict' function of 'rms' and the 'MIextract' function of the 'mitools' package, pooled using the 'MIcombine' function of 'mitools' and then exponentiated¹⁵.

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Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table 1. Hospital diagnosis and death registry codes used to identify incident health conditions of interest or prevalent conditions, for model covariates or exclusions.*

Health condition	ICD-9	ICD-10
Outcomes:		
Any fracture**	NA	S02, S12, S22, S32, S42, S52, S62, S72, S82, S92
Hip fracture**	NA	S72.0, S72.1, S72.2
Forearm fracture**	NA	S52
Covariates / exclusions:		
Adrenogenital / testicular disorders	255.2, 257	E25, E29
COPD	490, 491, 492, 494, 496	J43.1, J43.2, J43.8, J43.9, J44.0, J44.1, J44.8, J44.9
Malabsorption	579	K90
Malnutrition	262, 263.0, 263.1, 263.2, 263.8, 263.9	E43, E44.0, E44.1, E46
Renal impairment	582, 583, 585, 586	N03, N04, N05, N08.1-NO8.3, NO8.5, N11.1, N11.8, N11.9, N14, N18.2, N18.3, N18.4, N18.5, N18.6, N18.9, N19
Rheumatoid arthritis	<i>As defined in Forgetta et al.¹</i>	
Secondary osteoporosis	<i>Type 1 diabetes, chronic liver disease or osteogenesis imperfecta - As defined in Forgetta et al.¹</i>	
Thyroid disease	240-245	E00-E06
Vitamin D deficiency	268.0, 268.1, 268.2, 268.9	E55.0, E55.9, M83.2, M83.3, M83.8, M83.9

* = Additional data sources were also used for identifying prevalent conditions (e.g., from self-report medical conditions, self-report medication usage, and blood chemistry measurements).

** = Primary/main or secondary diagnosis in any position as recorded for hospital admissions. ICD-10 diagnoses only for incident outcomes.

NA = Not applicable.

Supplementary Table 2. Baseline characteristics of UK Biobank men, stratified according to those who experienced any fracture, hip fracture, or forearm fracture during follow-up, and for the cohort as a whole**.

<i>Baseline Characteristic</i> *§	<i>Participants with this event recorded during follow-up</i>			<i>All**</i>	Missing n (%)
	<i>Any fracture</i> (n =11,008)	<i>Hip fracture</i> (n=1,680)	<i>Forearm fracture</i> (n=1,366)	(n=205,973)	
<i>Sociodemographic & Lifestyle</i>					
Age (whole years)	60.0 (51.0-65.0)	63.0 (58.0-67.0)	57.0 (49.0-63.0)	58.0 (50.0-63.0)	0 (0.0)
BMI (kg/m ²)	27.1 (24.7-30.1)	26.3 (23.8-29.2)	27.1 (24.6-30.0)	27.3 (25.0-30.0)	925 (0.4)
Waist circumference (cm)	96.0 (89.0-104.0)	96.0 (88.0-103.5)	96.0 (89.0-104.0)	96.0 (89.0-103.0)	431 (0.2)
Vitamin D (nmol/L)	45.2 (30.5-61.1)	43.6 (29.1-59.4)	45.1 (30.5-60.8)	46.6 (32.2-62.1)	6,604 (3.2)
Ethnicity: not White	375 (3.4)	35 (2.1)	51 (3.8)	11,062 (5.4)	1,130 (0.5)
Education: Below A levels	5,351 (49.3)	868 (52.5)	597 (44.2)	91,140 (44.8)	2,353 (1.1)
A levels (high school)	694 (6.4)	82 (5.0)	96 (7.1)	14,171 (7.0)	
College/University	3,369 (31.0)	499 (30.2)	491 (36.3)	69,778 (34.3)	
Professional/Other	1,445 (13.3)	203 (12.3)	167 (12.4)	28,531 (14.0)	
Living with partner (yes)	7,594 (69.4)	1,145 (68.5)	959 (70.6)	157,464 (76.8)	838 (0.4)
Alcohol: Abstainers	3,035 (27.7)	548 (32.7)	371 (27.3)	57,175 (27.8)	480 (0.2)
Low	1,389 (12.7)	239 (14.3)	169 (12.4)	28,461 (13.9)	
Moderate	1,511 (13.8)	211 (12.6)	190 (14.0)	29,903 (14.6)	
Medium	1,504 (13.7)	214 (12.8)	179 (13.2)	29,595 (14.4)	
High	3,525 (32.2)	462 (27.6)	451 (33.2)	60,359 (29.4)	
Diet: High Red Meat	1,878 (17.4)	283 (17.3)	246 (18.4)	33,368 (16.5)	3,401 (1.7)
Low Red Meat	8,472 (78.6)	1,286 (78.4)	1,036 (77.3)	162,329 (80.1)	
No Red Meat	422 (3.9)	71 (4.3)	58 (4.3)	6,875 (3.4)	
PA: Insufficient	4,058 (39.3)	706 (44.8)	484 (37.3)	78,522 (40.3)	11,287 (5.5)
Sufficient	1,529 (14.8)	206 (13.1)	219 (16.9)	30,632 (15.7)	
Additional	4,731 (45.9)	665 (42.2)	593 (45.8)	85,532 (43.9)	
Smoking: Never	4,854 (44.4)	630 (37.7)	691 (50.8)	100,852 (49.2)	1,056 (0.5)
Previous	4,306 (39.3)	711 (42.5)	498 (36.6)	78,602 (38.4)	
Current	1,784 (16.3)	332 (19.8)	172 (12.6)	25,463 (12.4)	

<i>Baseline Characteristic</i> *§	<i>Participants with this event recorded during follow-up</i>			<i>All**</i>	
	<i>Any fracture</i> (<i>n</i> =11,008)	<i>Hip fracture</i> (<i>n</i> =1,680)	<i>Forearm fracture</i> (<i>n</i> =1,366)	(<i>n</i> =205,973)	Missing n (%)
<i>Prevalent health conditions and medication usage</i>					
Glucocorticoid use†	101 (0.9)	18 (1.1)	14 (1.0)	1,185 (0.6)	69 (0.0)
Fracture (in past 5 years)	1,630 (14.8)	233 (13.9)	234 (17.1)	17,735 (8.6)	0 (0.0)
Renal impairment	144 (1.3)	34 (2.0)	14 (1.0)	1,450 (0.7)	0 (0.0)
Secondary osteoporosis†	115 (1.0)	23 (1.4)	11 (0.8)	816 (0.4)	0 (0.0)
Thyroid disease	273 (2.5)	45 (2.7)	20 (1.5)	4,418 (2.1)	0 (0.0)
COPD	194 (1.8)	56 (3.3)	12 (0.9)	1,860 (0.9)	0 (0.0)
Primary hyperparathyroidism	4 (0.0)	1 (0.1)	0 (0.0)	34 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Anticonvulsant use	360 (3.3)	80 (4.8)	32 (2.3)	3,158 (1.5)	69 (0.0)
Opioid use	788 (7.2)	162 (9.6)	84 (6.1)	9,473 (4.6)	69 (0.0)
Vitamin D supplementation	114 (1.0)	29 (1.7)	12 (0.9)	1,235 (0.6)	69 (0.0)
No. Meds: 0	3,024 (27.5)	338 (20.1)	436 (31.9)	66,105 (32.1)	69 (0.0)
1-2	3,228 (29.3)	442 (26.3)	436 (31.9)	67,342 (32.7)	
3-4	2,119 (19.3)	392 (23.3)	241 (17.6)	38,035 (18.5)	
5+	2,635 (23.9)	507 (30.2)	253 (18.5)	34,422 (16.7)	
<i>Hormone variables</i>					
Testosterone (nmol/L)	11.7 (9.4-14.3)	12.0 (9.5-14.6)	11.7 (9.5-14.3)	11.6 (9.4-14.1)	0 (0.0)
Testosterone (ng/dL)	337 (271-412)	346 (274-421)	337 (274-412)	334 (271-406)	0 (0.0)
SHBG (nmol/L)	39.8 (29.8-52.5)	45.5 (34.3-59.9)	39.3 (29.2-52.6)	36.9 (27.9-48.1)	16,388 (8.0)
cFT (pmol/L)	204.6 (168.7-246.5)	191.4 (157.5-231.0)	207.5 (170.7-249.3)	213.6 (177.9-255.3)	16,388 (8.0)

† = Defined using definitions provided in Forgetta et al.

* = Continuous variables (age, BMI, cholesterol, waist circumference, testosterone, SHBG, cFT) represented as median (interquartile range); other variables as percentages (numbers) per category.

** = Summary data presented for data after excluding men taking androgens, anti-androgen, 5 α -reductase, estrogen, anti-estrogen, or progesterone medications or men with infertility, prior orchidectomy, pituitary disease, adrenogenital or testicular disorders, or missing baseline testosterone concentration.

§ = BMI, body mass index (kg/m²); Education, Educational attainment; PA, level of physical activity categories (min/week; see Methods); Alcohol, level of alcohol consumption (standard units of alcohol consumed/week; see Methods); Smoking, smoking status; SHBG, sex hormone binding globulin; cFT, free testosterone calculated using the Vermeulen formula.

Supplementary Table 3. Estimates of 10-year predicted risk (%) for fracture and the absolute risk (difference) for UK Biobank male participants with a baseline hormone concentration equal to the median of the lowest quintile compared with the median of the highest quintile(s) (ref). Presented values are marginal predictions from model 3 at the respective quintile medians, controlling for common confounders and risk factors at baseline (age, time of blood sampling, time of blood sampling, UK country (England, Scotland, Wales), ethnicity (white vs not white), alcohol consumption, smoking status, BMI, use of glucocorticoids, fracture in past five years, renal impairment, secondary osteoporosis, thyroid disease, educational attainment, living with partner, diet (red meat: high vs low vs none), physical activity, waist circumference, COPD, and use of anticonvulsants, opioids, and vitamin D supplements, with the number of medications included as a proxy for overall comorbidity status) as well as the competing risk of death due to other causes. Values are pooled estimates from the analyses of multiply-imputed datasets.

Exposure	10-year risk (%)	Outcome		
		Any fracture	Hip fracture	Forearm fracture
T	Q1	2.39	0.22	0.36
	Q2	2.31	0.21	0.33
	Difference	0.08	0.01	0.03
	Q5	2.56	0.28	0.36
	Q2	2.31	0.21	0.33
	Difference	0.25	0.07	0.03
cFT	Q5	2.16	0.21	0.31
	Q1	2.70	0.30	0.43
	Difference	-0.54	-0.08	-0.12
SHBG	Q5	2.88	0.33	0.47
	Q1	2.10	0.18	0.30
	Difference	0.78	0.14	0.17

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1. Study flow diagram.

Supplementary Figure 2. Estimated association of baseline serum testosterone concentration with risk of fracture. (a–c) Model 1. Estimates adjusted for time of blood sampling, geographic region and participant age. (d–f) Model 2. Estimates adjusted for model 1 covariates plus other FRAX-related covariates: body mass index, fracture in past five years, smoking status, glucocorticoid use, secondary osteoporosis, and alcohol consumption. Shaded areas are 95% confidence intervals and the locations of hazard ratios (medians of sample quintiles, as presented in Table 2) are indicated. Horizontal axes are truncated to exclude values outside of boundary knots, where data are sparsely distributed and trends are constrained to linearity.

Supplementary Figure 3. Estimated association of baseline cFT concentration with risk of fracture.

(a–c) Model 1. Estimates adjusted for time of blood sampling, geographic region, thyroid disease, renal impairment, ethnicity (white vs. not white), participant age. (d–f) Model 2. Estimates adjusted for model 1 covariates plus other FRAX-related covariates: body mass index, fracture in past five years, smoking status, glucocorticoid use, secondary osteoporosis, and alcohol consumption. Shaded areas are 95% confidence intervals and the locations of hazard ratios (medians of sample quintiles, as presented in Table 3) are indicated. Horizontal axes are truncated to exclude values outside of boundary knots, where data are sparsely distributed and trends are constrained to linearity.

Supplementary Figure 4. Estimated association of baseline SHBG concentration with risk of fracture.

(a–c) Model 1. Estimates adjusted for time of blood sampling, geographic region and participant age.

(d–f) Model 2. Estimates adjusted for model 1 covariates plus other FRAX-related covariates: body mass index, fracture in past five years, smoking status, glucocorticoid use, secondary osteoporosis, and alcohol consumption. Shaded areas are 95% confidence intervals and the locations of hazard ratios (medians of sample quintiles, as presented in Table 3) are indicated. Horizontal axes are

truncated to exclude values outside of boundary knots, where data are sparsely distributed and trends are constrained to linearity.

